

Beyond Task Volume and Time: A Comprehensive Study of Workload Perception and Coping Mechanisms in the Workplace

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Abstract

This study, part of the SAFE-Coach project funded by the German Federal Ministry of Economics and Labour, investigates the multifaceted nature of workload management in HR contexts. We aimed to understand the interplay between physical, cognitive, and social competencies and their influence on perceived workload. Using a sample of 109 German residents, our research employed a quantitative approach using self-report questionnaires based on a 5-point Likert scale to analyse the impact of different factors on workload perceptions. Our findings indicate that interpersonal and social competencies play a crucial role in workload management, with participants rating organisational skills, reliability, and situational intelligence as highly effective. Cognitive skills, particularly problem-solving and decision-making skills, were also significant and enhanced the ability to manage workload effectively. Physical demands, such as prolonged sitting and associated discomfort, were less influential but notable for their negative impact on productivity and stress levels.

Environmental factors, including job security, time pressure and workplace relationships, were found to have a significant impact on workload perceptions. Cultural and industry-specific expectations further nuanced these perceptions, highlighting the importance of contextual awareness in workload management strategies. This study contributes to the understanding of workload dynamics by integrating multiple competencies and environmental factors, providing insights for developing effective interventions tailored to different professional settings. Future research should further explore these relationships, particularly through longitudinal studies, to better understand the temporal dynamics of workload management.

Keywords: workload management, interpersonal competencies, cognitive abilities, physical demands, environmental factors, self-assessment, workload perception, job satisfaction, stress management, industry-specific workload, cultural influence on workload, NASA-TLX, HR management strategies, work-life balance, German workforce, employee productivity, workplace interventions

1. Introduction

As part of the SAFE-Coach project, which is funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, our objective was to develop an avatar with coaching capabilities within HR contexts. To this end, we conducted a study to investigate people's behavior regarding the management of high workloads. Our findings provide valuable insights that will assist the avatar's developers in programming.

According to the Cambridge online dictionary, the term workload can be defined as "the amount of work to be done, especially by a particular person or machine, in a given period of time." Some researchers suggest that the definition of workload can be divided into three parts (Cain, 2007; Lysaght et al., 1989):

1. How much work/how many tasks need to be done
2. How much time is available for the work to be done
3. How a person feels and thinks about 1. and 2. /perceived workload

The relationship between task volume, time available, and subjective perception is essential to understanding different workload models. The interaction between these elements shows how the overall workload is experienced:

- **Volume of tasks** refers to the number of tasks assigned or the amount of work to be done. The volume of tasks directly impacts an individual's perception of their workload. A higher volume can lead to feelings of overwhelm or stress.

- **Time available** refers to the time allotted to complete tasks. Limited time can increase perceived workload, even if the volume of tasks remains constant.

- **Subjective Perception** is how an individual feels about the volume of tasks and the time available. This perception is influenced by personal factors such as stress tolerance, motivation and coping mechanisms.

The incorporation of these elements into different workload models varies. For instance, performance-

based models may prioritize the balance between task completion and accuracy, whereas subjective models focus on how individuals perceive their workload. Overall, Cain (2007) and Casner & Gore (2010) concur that there are different definitions of workload, contingent on one's perspective or culturally appropriate view.

A variety of measures of workload exist, including performance measures (e.g., activity, task analysis, accuracy, and speed), subjective measures (e.g., numerical or comparative), and physiological measures (e.g., heart rate) (Casner & Gore, 2010). Researchers such as Casner & Gore (2010) have highlighted the NASA TLX as a popular subjective workload measure that assesses six dimensions: effort, frustration, physical demand, temporal demand, and cognitive demand. These dimensions provide different views of workload.

Comparing the NASA-TLX with other subjective measures highlights similarities and differences:

- **Similarities:** Like the NASA-TLX, other subjective measures often consider psychological factors, such as perceived stress or frustration, in addition to workload-related physical demands.

- **Differences:** Other measures may focus on different aspects of subjective workload. For example, some may emphasise the emotional impact of workload, while others may be more concerned with cognitive demands.

These dimensions provide different views of workload. A comparison of the NASA-TLX with other subjective measures highlights similarities and differences.

Similarities: Like the NASA-TLX, other subjective measures often consider psychological factors, such as perceived stress or frustration, in addition to workload-related physical demands.

However, the NASA-TLX, like our study, places greater emphasis on the third part of the common definition of workload than on the other parts, which is subjective perception (see also Miller, 2001). Our study focused on the subjective measure of workload because it was based on self-reporting through an online survey.

Contextual factors contribute to workload perception in different ways, for instance, through cultural or industry-specific expectations. When it comes to cultural influence, cultural factors can significantly influence workload perceptions and coping mechanisms. For example, cross-cultural studies have shown that cultural norms influence perceptions of stress, work-life balance, and productivity. In some cultures, a high workload may be seen as a sign of success, while in others, it may be a sign of poor time management (Welmilla & Semasinghe, 2022; Zhang (2020).

Cultural attitudes can also shape coping mechanisms, with some societies emphasizing personal resilience while others emphasizing external support systems (Linscott, 2014). Regarding the influence of industry, industry-specific factors contribute to workload in unique ways. For example, sectors such as healthcare, education, and technology may have different demands and expectations. In healthcare, the workload may increase due to emergencies or pandemics, while in education, the workload may fluctuate according to the academic calendar. In the technology industry, project requirements can change rapidly, leading to increased workloads and potential burnout. It is therefore crucial to understand these industry-specific factors in order to effectively tailor workload management strategies (Govindaras et al., 2023; Martinez-Vazquez, 2021).

The aim of our study was to investigate three key questions:

- 1) What prevents someone from managing their workload?
- 2) What helps someone cope with the workload?
- 3) What influences workload or the perception of too much workload?

In short, in our study, we were interested in the influence of different factors on workload and how they hinder or help coping with it.

This article focuses on the physical, cognitive, and social/interpersonal competencies and demands, as well as the framework conditions necessary for coping with workload, which were part of the study through self-assessment.

H1: Interpersonal and social competencies support workload management

Different interpersonal and social competencies are essential depending on the job profile. For example, Fleishman (1992) identified 21 interpersonal and social competencies that can be used in job analysis interviews.

They appear to compromise personality traits as well as emotional and social intelligence. When thinking about personality traits as competencies for a job, other research on coping with workload through personality and social and emotional intelligence can be used as sources. This research is presented in Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024b), which focuses on person-related factors and their influence on workload coping.

H2: Cognitive competencies support workload management.

Regarding the cognitive competencies needed for coping with workload, in a more recent study by Siswanto et al. (2019), education was shown to be a helpful resource for coping with workload — in addition to working comfort and existing skills required for the tasks. Also, individuals with higher levels of education were more motivated. Additionally, an increase in workload that still allowed employees to work comfortably, that was appropriate to their skills, and that required them to perform tasks according to the standard even improved bank employees' performance. However, there may be a cultural bias as the study was only conducted in Indonesia.

Similarly, the study by Gonzalez (2005) found that those with lower levels of intelligence were more likely to perform less well and may have less motivation as they were less likely to improve their performance even on the same level of difficulty/easy tasks than those who were more intelligent. According to Gonzalez (2005), cognitive ability was more helpful in coping with workload when scoring higher on the Raven Standard Matrices test. However, as the participants were only students from a US university, no comparison can be made with people from other countries or other professions/general samples.

H3: Physical demands contribute to workload

The Disability Research Institute at the University of Illinois at Champaign-Urbana & Northwestern University Rehabilitation Institute of Chicago (2021)

report on the frequency of physical demands in different jobs and categorise them in a cluster-like hierarchy — from climbing to standing and moving heavy or light objects.

Similarly, Fleishman (1992) reported on physical, psychomotor, and perceptual abilities to describe the demands of a job — such as scotopic vision and coordination of movements.

In terms of the physical demands and skills needed to cope with the workload, Perry et al. (2008) found that a physical demand could be more demanding during a cognitive demand, for example, jogging rather than standing. DiDomenico and Nussbaum (2008) found an overall higher NASA TXL score when the physical demand was higher. However, they controlled for body mass index, and the inclusion criterion was that participants could lift 20% of their body weight.

We, therefore, hypothesise that physical demand will influence workload, especially in jobs where cognitive demand is essential.

H4: Environmental factors contribute to the perception of workload as strain.

Environmental effects could also influence workload, such as noise, financial worries, lack of job security, insecure job situation, time pressure, overtime, unfavourable/poor working environment, private interpersonal problems (partnership, family, ...), professional interpersonal problems, perfectionism, procrastination, pressure to perform, lack of interest, lack of competencies/skills.

A study by Van Droogenbroeck et al. (2014) showed that teachers' professional relationships, especially with colleagues, influence emotional distress. Similarly, the influence of supervisors' relationships on emotional distress was influenced by the level of autonomy given to teachers. However, older teachers had less emotional distress than younger teachers.

In Sturm et al.'s (2019) study, objective measures of overtime correlated with subjective work-related stress and strain, so we assume that it can be seen as an overall strain and influence the perception of workload as a strain and its assessment on a NASA-TXL-like measure.

In a cross-cultural study by Scherer (2009) with data from all European countries except France and Eastern European countries, employees with temporary contracts report a range of problems, including lower levels of happiness and life satisfaction, as well as worries about finances and higher potential for conflict between romantic partners. Overall, they suggest that it is the lack of job security in terms of contract duration, rather than unfavourable working conditions, that triggers more negative outcomes, such as private interpersonal problems.

In the study by Brennan et al. (2022), age had an effect on work-related stress. The older a farmer was, the more stress they perceived. They found the same for people with financial problems, meaning that those with more debt experienced more stress at work. Similarly, in Daneshvar et al. (2021), 38% of health workers expressed anxiety due to financial worries, 26% expressed anxiety due to unsympathetic leadership - which may be related to strains in professional relationships. For 30% of health workers surveyed, the high workload was responsible for anxiety, and the source of the high workload was described as overtime during the pandemic due to reduced staffing levels and increasing numbers of COVID-19 patients.

As suggested by Galy et al. (2017), it can be criticised that NASA-TLX measures workload as one dimension, but it would be better to consider each dimension alone. It was also the aim of our study not to calculate a global score, but to analyse the items separately as representations of a dimension and later also to test for correlations with personality dimensions (see Wortmann & Panahian Fard 2024b).

In addressing the issue of time pressure, personality differences offer an important explanatory variable. This concept has been explored in depth by Omohehin & Smith (2019), who found that individual personality traits can influence how effectively someone copes with time pressure. Further exploration of this relationship will also be featured in upcoming work by Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024b), which aims to delve deeper into the nuances of personality and workload coping mechanisms.

The phenomenon of procrastination, which often contributes to increased perceptions of workload and

stress, will be examined in depth in the same forthcoming publication by Wortmann & Panahian Fard (2024b), which will include a review of the existing literature on procrastination, focusing on how it affects workload management and what strategies might mitigate its effects on work-related stress.

2. Methods

2.1 Sample

The data set for the analysis consists of 109 participants. In terms of gender distribution, slightly more than half of the participants, 53.2% or 58 individuals, identify as female. A smaller percentage, 44% or 48 individuals, identify as male. There is one participant, representing 0.9% of the total, who identifies with a gender categorised as 'other'. In addition, there are two participants, representing 1.8% of the total, whose gender responses are missing from the dataset.

Table 1 participants gender distribution

Gender Distribution	Percentage (%)	Number (N)
Female	53.2	58
Male	44.0	48
Other	0.9	1
Missing	1.8	2
Total	100.0	109

Looking at the age demographics of the participants, the data shows a normal distribution, which is a typical bell-shaped curve indicating that most values are clustered around a central point. The majority of participants, representing the middle part of this curve, are between the ages of 35 and 54. This age distribution suggests that the study is predominantly a mid-life demographic, which may reflect certain social, economic or health characteristics typical of this age group.

Geographically, the vast majority of participants in the study, 92.7% or 101 people, live in Germany. This high concentration of participants from a single country may affect the generalisability of the study's findings to other populations. The employment data show that a significant proportion, 33.9% or 37 participants, work in

clerical or technical occupations. These jobs typically require specialised technical or administrative skills. A further 18.3% or 20 people are in middle management, which usually involves supervisory responsibilities and a higher level of organisational involvement. In addition, 16.5% or 18 participants are self-employed, indicating a subset of the sample engaged in entrepreneurial or freelance activities, reflecting greater autonomy and flexibility in their working lives.

Table 2 Employment Type

Employment Type	Percentage (%)	Number (N)
Clerical/Technical	33.9	37
Middle Management	18.3	20
Self-Employed	16.5	18
Total	68.7	75

2.2 Instruments

In our research project, we preferred to operationalise items with a 5-point Likert scale, as this lends itself well to modelling. Participants could give answers between *Not at all* (=1) and *Very much* (=5).

Firstly, the first battery of questions was created by developing a personality questionnaire, inspired by IPIP Home (2022) (see Tab 3.) The aim was to focus on work as the primary environment. With this in mind, the items were chosen accordingly to create a work-personality-like inventory.

Table 3 Personality factors with facets (German and English)

Dimension	Items
Conscientiousness	C1: Ich tue oft mehr als von mir erwartet wird. / I often do more than is expected of me.
	C2 Ich gebe alles, um erfolgreich zu sein. / I give everything to be successful.
	C3 Wenn ich etwas anfangе, bringe ich es auch zu Ende. / When I start something, I finish it.

		C4 Ich kann viele Dinge gleichzeitig erledigen. / I can do many things at the same time.
Neuroticism		<p>N1: Ich mache mir oft um Dinge Sorgen, für die es im Nachhinein keinen Grund gibt. / I often worry about things for which there is no reason in retrospect.</p> <p>N2: Ich brauche die Bestätigung der anderen. / I need the affirmation of others.</p> <p>N3: Ich schäme mich vor anderen, auch wenn ich einen kleinen Fehler begangen habe. / I am ashamed in front of others, even if I have made a small mistake.</p> <p>N4: Meine Entscheidungen sind leicht durch andere beeinflussbar. / My decisions are easily influenced by others.</p> <p>N5 Ich zweifle schnell daran, ob ich einer Aufgabe gewachsen bin. / I quickly doubt whether I am up to a task.</p>
Agreeableness		<p>A1: Ich helfe gerne anderen. / I like to help others.</p> <p>A2: Ich bin leicht zufrieden zu stellen. / I am easy to please.</p> <p>A3: Ich kann mich an eine neue Umgebung gut anpassen. / I can adapt well to a new environment.</p> <p>A4: Ich weiß nicht, wie ich mich in sozialen Situationen verhalten soll. / I don't know how to behave in social situations.</p>
Openness to Experience		<p>OE1: Ich bin vielseitig interessiert. / I have a wide range of interests.</p> <p>OE2: Ich lerne gerne Neues. / I like to learn new things.</p> <p>OE3: Ich finde gerne heraus, wie Dinge funktionieren. / I like to find out how things work.</p> <p>OE4: Ich nehme mir gerne Zeit, um über die Dinge zu reflektieren. / I like to take time to reflect on things.</p>
<i>Extraversion</i>		<i>Not found</i>
(Frequent/longer) (Frequent/longer)	Sitting	Physical strength, and (Frequent/longer)

Standing and Carrying heavy/light objects over long/short distances were taken from the report of the Disability Research Institute at the University of Illinois at Champaign-Urbana & Northwestern University Rehabilitation Institute of Chicago (2021).

Scotopic vision and long-sightedness or near-sightedness were taken from the perceptual abilities' list in Fleishman's Job Analysis Handbook (1992). In the same vein, reaction time and/or reaction speed, hand motor functions/light-fingeredness and precise control of movements were taken from the list of psychomotor aptitudes, while coordination of movements was taken from the list of physical aptitudes.

Secondly, we were interested in creating a model by implementing questionnaires measuring cognitive, physical, and social demands to determine what might help people cope with the workload.

A battery of questions was created to assess the necessary interpersonal and social competencies and another battery to assess the physical demands of the job, inspired by the Fleishman recruitment questionnaires, because cognitive and physical abilities, as well as interpersonal and social competencies that are relevant in different types of jobs may therefore be relevant for coping with workload if these abilities and competencies are actually needed to be accepted in a job or to do a job successfully.

Thirdly, we asked participants to rate their mental, physical and temporal demands, as well as their performance, effort and frustration. An item for social strain/stress was added because we were interested how they compared with other employees on an additional scale.

The scale was inspired by the NASA-TLX — a multidimensional instrument for subjective assessment of workload (mental, physical, and temporal demands, performance, effort, and frustration).

Finally, it aimed for answering the following question: What do you think is the most important determinant of workload in your job? As mentioned in the introduction, each dimension could be seen as a different view of what can be defined as workload.

Fourthly, the creation of items for the question about stresses that might influence the workload experience was inspired by Voigt (2021, pp. 55-59) and the literature on perfectionism, procrastination, and lack of interest and competence, as mentioned in the introduction.

Some of the added items could be summarised as variables for working conditions, such as unfavourable working environment, pressure to perform, time pressure, noise, safety at work, overtime and straining work relationships. These variables can be used as both personal and environmental factors for interpretation.

2.3 Translation and participant recruitment

The cognitive, interpersonal, and physical demands were taken from existing French literature (Fleishman, 1992 & 1998), and the questionnaire was then translated into German and English using deepl.com (DeepL, 2024). The personality items were first written in German and English and then translated into French. Other questions and their items were first written in German and then translated into English and French using existing translations (in the case of NASA TLX) or deepl.com. However, a dataset in French or English was not used for further analysis due to insufficient numbers of participants.

Reminders for participation were also posted on LinkedIn and sent to private contacts, including Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook. We also shared the survey in English, French, and German Facebook and LinkedIn groups, which are specifically designed to share surveys but also related to New Work or HR, specifically workload.

3. Results

We calculated mean scores of the workload categories E) environmental factors, P) physical factors, S) social factors, and O) other factors.

In terms of environmental factors, mental demands show that 1e) *mental flexibility*, 2e) *classification/filing of information*, 3e) *readiness of mind*, and 4e) *oral comprehension and expression* were selected as the top

4 competencies that could best cope with workload or high work demands.

When asked about physical demands that were considered to be an obstacle to coping with high workload, 1p) *frequent/long sitting*, 2p) *long or short-sightedness*, 3p) *(frequent/long) exertion/physical strength*, and 4p) *frequent or long-standing* were assessed as the most relevant on average.

The social and interpersonal skills that were named as most helpful on average in coping with the workload of the job, were: 1s) *organisational skills*, 2s) *reliability*, 3s) *verbal reasoning skills*, and 4s) *the ability to act correctly in different situations (situational intelligence)*.

Among other pressures that lead to a higher perceived workload, on average, were assessed 1o) *time pressure*, 2o) *pressure to perform*, 3o) *perfectionism*, and 4o) *overtime* as primarily relevant (see table 3, p.10).

For environmental factors, our study is consistent with Hakanen et al. (2017), who emphasise that competencies such as mental flexibility, information classification, mental readiness, and oral comprehension are critical for effectively managing high workload demands. This supports our initial findings, suggesting that enhanced mental skills can significantly act as a buffer against the negative effects of environmental workload demands.

Physical demands identified as barriers to effective workload management included frequent or prolonged sitting, visual problems, heavy physical exertion, and constant standing. This is consistent with the findings of Mänttari et al. (2023), who emphasized that such physical demands in home care lead to reduced recovery from work, suggesting the need for targeted strategies to reduce physical workload to improve worker recovery and productivity.

Social and interpersonal skills, such as organisational skills, reliability, verbal reasoning, and situational intelligence, were confirmed to be beneficial in workload management. Our findings are consistent with those of Hakanen et al. (2017), who discussed the role of job crafting as a proactive approach to reconfigure job demands and resources, thereby promoting better

workload management through enhanced social and personal competencies.

Furthermore, our findings regarding the pressures contributing to perceived workload, such as time constraints, performance demands, perfectionism, and overtime, are supported by the broader literature, which recognizes these factors as prevalent stressors in various work settings (Bowling et al., 2015). These pressures are universally recognized as significant contributors to perceived workload, necessitating comprehensive strategies to mitigate their effects.

The integration of job crafting, as discussed by Hakanen et al. (2017), offers a promising avenue for individuals and organizations to adaptively modify work roles to better fit workers' abilities and limitations, potentially leading to improved job satisfaction and reduced burnout. This strategy not only assists in coping with high-demand situations but also fosters a resilient and engaged workforce capable of sustaining high performance over time.

Our study highlights the multifaceted nature of workload management and underscores the importance of addressing physical, social, and environmental dimensions to improve overall employee well-being and productivity.

4. Discussion

The first hypothesis, which posits that 'interpersonal and social competencies contribute to coping with workload', is substantiated by the valuable feedback from our participants. Their responses underscore the pivotal role of these competencies in effective workload management. The importance of social interaction and communication skills in navigating workplace dynamics, collaborating with colleagues, and alleviating stress caused by workload is clearly evident. Interpersonal and social competencies appear to be the most relevant contributors to workload management.

The second hypothesis which suggested that 'cognitive skills contribute to workload management' is also supported. Participants considered these competencies to be the second most important factor in their ability to cope with workload. Cognitive skills such

as problem solving, decision making, and critical thinking play a crucial role in managing tasks efficiently and reducing perceived workload.

The third hypothesis, suggesting that physical demands significantly influence workload, is not supported by the data. The research findings only suggest that about the average of participants see frequent and prolonged sitting as adversely impactful on the individual's ability to manage workload, possibly due to physical discomforts such as back and neck problems. This, in turn, hampers concentration and overall productivity, a factor that could be further researched in future research.

The fourth hypothesis, which suggests that environmental factors significantly contribute to the perception of workload as a strain, is supported by our data. Our findings reveal that time pressure and pressure to perform are more influential in shaping this perception than factors like perfectionism or overtime. This aligns with the NASA-TXL workload model, which emphasises time pressure and pressure to perform as key dimensions, but not perfectionism or overtime. These insights are crucial for understanding and addressing workplace stress.

According to the participants' feedback, interpersonal and social competencies are considered the most useful in coping with workload. Close behind, cognitive skills are seen as the second most useful in coping with workload. The lack of social and cognitive competencies appears to have a greater impact on the perception of workload. In addition, stressors that increase perceptions of workload, such as time pressure and pressure to perform, seem more influential than physical demands.

Practical Implications

The findings can be translated into practical interventions for the workplace. Employers can implement interventions to address social, cognitive, and environmental stressors. On the one hand, improving workplace relationships and social skills can be encouraged by open channels of communication and team-building exercises. On the other hand, offering flexible working hours or project schedules can reduce environmental stress. Digital collaboration tools, such as video conferencing and messaging platforms, can help

maintain communication and teamwork among remote workers, reducing social isolation and increasing productivity. In order to reduce physical stress, workplaces can promote ergonomic office furniture or standing desks to reduce the effects of prolonged sitting.

Training programmes focusing on improving coping skills can play an essential role in workload management. Mindfulness training, for example, can help employees manage stress effectively. In addition, professional development programmes can improve cognitive and social skills, such as problem-solving skills, decision-making strategies and effective communication techniques (Harris & Bacon, 2019).

Digital solutions can also help manage workload. Digital tools like task management software and productivity apps such as SAFE-Coach can help employees organise and prioritise tasks, improving efficiency and reducing stress. This is particularly the case in remote working contexts.

Employers should also consider the impact of remote working on workload perceptions and ensure that employees have the tools to achieve an effective work-life balance.

Digital self-assessment tools can provide insight into employees' perceptions of workload, allowing them to identify stressors and develop coping strategies.

Limitations

The study acknowledges its limitations, including lack of generalisability due to sample size and possible translation issues, potential bias due to social desirability, and contextual effects. Future research with more diverse, larger samples and longitudinal studies could improve generalisability and show patterns over time.

Particularly, the English translation could have been more precise in distinguishing between safety at work and job security in terms of contract type.

We failed to find enough participants for the English and French versions. However, it would have been interesting considering that Cegarra and Morgado (2009) compared the results of the English and French

versions and showed slightly different results for the same tasks.

Bad weather conditions and health problems were not included in the assessment, as they were mentioned as relevant in Scherer (2009), for example. Health was particularly not explicitly listed among other strains, since its term could be biased due to the Covid pandemic and because, in a future study, as part of the SAFE-COACH project, we will focus more on well-being in general.

Our instrument is also limited in interpretation and generalisation due to social desirability and lack of objectivity of the assessment.

The comparability of the results could be affected by the (group of) reference effect, which means that people have had different experiences in their lives before, which can affect their evaluation differently (Heine, 2015). Similarly, the context effect may influence the assessment (Hart, 2006).

Further research

The study provides valuable insights into how different factors influence the perception of coping with workload. However, further research is needed to explore the dynamic interactions between these factors and their cumulative impact on organisational outcomes. Research broaching the issue of the interplay of different factors could provide a more comprehensive understanding of workload dynamics and inform more effective workload management strategies. For example, the relationship between personality, task characteristics, and task preference and their interaction warrants further investigation.

Future studies should also explore how specific personality traits influence coping mechanisms, which will play a key role in our upcoming research paper. We also suggest addressing remote workings' impact on workload perceptions and coping mechanism by examining environmental and social factors such as work-life balance, home office arrangements and digital collaboration. Research has shown that ensuring a healthy work-life balance and a conducive home-office

environment can reduce workload stress (Kleiminger & Wortmann, 2021).

By exploring the nuanced interactions between these factors, we can gain a deeper understanding of how they collectively shape workload perceptions and coping mechanisms. This understanding can pave the way for the development of comprehensive workplace interventions that incorporate strategies to holistically address physical, cognitive, and environmental stressors, providing a beacon of hope for improved workplace wellness.

Statement: Conflict of Interest

The authors declare partial involvement in the development of a highly modern commercial product as well as participation in a financially supported research project. Despite this involvement, the authors affirm that they have no vested interest in any specific outcomes of this research. The primary objective was to obtain valid, non-biased data essential for the development of the product's base model.

Furthermore, the authors confirm that all data acquisition and analysis procedures were conducted in strict adherence to the universally accepted principles of ethical and professional conduct. This ensures the integrity and credibility of the research findings and their applicability in broader scientific and practical contexts.

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Table 3 Workload Dimensions, ranks and mean values

WL dimensions	Items and mean values			
	Rank	1.	2.	3.
Mental demands	Mental flexibility (<i>M</i> =4.33)	Filing information (<i>M</i> =4.27)	Readiness of mind (<i>M</i> =4.21)	Verbal comprehension and expression (<i>M</i> =4.21)
Physical demands	Frequent/longer seating (<i>M</i> = 3.06)	Long or short sightedness (<i>M</i> =2.16)	(Frequent/longer) physical strength (<i>M</i> =1.69)	Frequent/longer standing (<i>M</i> =1.68)
Social and interpersonal competencies/demands	Organisational skills (<i>M</i> =4.57)	Reliability (<i>M</i> =4.54)	Verbal reasoning skills (<i>M</i> =4.42)	The ability to act correctly in different situations (situational intelligence) (<i>M</i> =4.39)
Other strains related to workload	Time pressure (<i>M</i> =3.41)	Pressure to outperform (<i>M</i> =3.38)	Perfectionism (<i>M</i> =2.99)	Overtime (<i>M</i> =2.92)

Note. Ranking of the most frequent named competencies/demands or strains